

THE REACTION BETWEEN AMMONIUM OXALATE AND IODINE

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The reaction between ammonium oxalate and iodine has been studied both in light and in dark. The results obtained are similar to those obtained in the case of potassium oxalate and iodine. Thus, in dark the reaction is unimolecular with respect to iodine and ammonium oxalate, but becomes semi-molecular with respect to iodine in light. The dark temperature coefficient is high and has a value of about 5 between temperatures 30° and 60°. The temperature coefficient falls to 3.4 for light reaction. The reaction is retarded by KI and shows photochemical after-effect which increases with the increase in the period of pre-illumination. The relation between intensity and velocity obeys square root relationship and the primary process consists in the atomisation of iodine molecules.

Although the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine, dissolved in KI, has been studied extensively (Dhar, *Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1916, 16, 1097; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 748; 1923, 123, 1853; *Z. Electrochem.*, 1925, 31, 621; Berthoud and Bellenot, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 307; Griffith and a McKeown, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 752; Abel and Hilferding, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1935, 172A, 353), yet the reaction between ammonium oxalate and iodine has not been investigated.

Dark Reaction

Order of Reaction with respect to I₂ dissolved in KI etc.—As the reaction is very slow at low temperatures, the temperatures used were above 30°. Integration method was used to determine the order of the reaction and it was found that unimolecular formulae gave constant results. The order of reaction with respect to ammonium oxalate was determined by Ostwald's isolation method. It comes out to be 1. Thus, the total order of the reaction is 2. The temperature coefficient of the reaction between 40° and 60° is about 5. The value is much lower than that when K₂C₂O₄ is used. It is found in several reactions that ammonium salts have a marked accelerating effect. The temperature coefficient of a reaction is determined by its acceleration, and since ammonium oxalate reaction is quicker at low temperature, its temperature coefficient is consequently smaller than that for K₂C₂O₄ and I₂ reaction. The reaction is retarded by KI, and the retardation increases with the concentration of KI. The results supporting the above conclusions are summarised below.

TABLE I

$I_2 = 0.000977M$. $KI = 0.00937M$. Amm. oxalate = $0.166M$. Temp. = 60° .

Time,	$a-x$.	$k_1 \times 60$.	$k_1' \times 60$.	$K_0 \times 60$.
0 mins.	12.7	...	...	...
6	11.0	0.0104	0.0833	0.233
14	9.2	0.0100	0.0757	0.250
21	7.7	0.0103	0.0751	0.238
31	5.6	0.0114	0.0771	0.229

TABLE II

Conc. of oxalate.	$k_1 60^\circ$.	$k_1 50^\circ$.	$k_1 40^\circ$.	$k_1 \frac{60^\circ}{50^\circ}$.	$k_1 \frac{50^\circ}{40^\circ}$.	Ratio of conc.	Ratio of $k_1 60^\circ$.
0.166M (a)	0.0114	0.0022	0.00049	5.18	5.5	$\frac{a}{b} = 2$	1.98
0.0833 (b)	0.0058	0.0012	0.00021	5.28	5.2	$\frac{b}{c} = 2$	
0.0416 (c)	0.0038	0.00086	0.00013	5.0	5.1		1.7

TABLE III

Conc. of ammonium oxalate = $0.166M$.

Conc. of KI	0.00937 M	0.02437 M	0.03937 M	0.05437 M
$k_1 60^\circ$	0.0114	0.0039	0.0028	0.0021

Energy of Activation

Arrhenius' empirical relation, $\frac{d \log k}{dt} = \frac{E}{RT^2}$ gives the value 34850 calories for E , the energy of activation.

Following Lewis that Z molecules enter into collision per second and then adopting the simplest possible form of distribution law, the fraction of molecules possessing energies greater than E_1 and E_2 are given by $e^{-E_1/RT}$ and $e^{-E_2/RT}$. The chance therefore that two molecules in collision will be such that the energy of one exceeds E_1 , and the energy of the other exceeds E_2 is $e^{-E_1/RT} \times e^{-E_2/RT} = e^{-(E_1+E_2)/RT} = e^{-E/RT}$.

Thus the total number of molecules which collide with a joint energy exceeding E is $Ze^{-E/RT}$, where ' Z ' is the number of collisions per second between the reacting molecules and given by $\sqrt{2} \pi \sigma^2 \bar{u} n^2$ where σ is the molecular diameter, $\bar{u}$, the root mean square velocity and ' n ', the number of molecules per c.c.

Thus, the total number of activated molecules colliding is $\sqrt{2} \cdot \pi \sigma^2 \times \bar{u} n^2 e^{-E/RT}$.

For molecules which are different we have, $\pi \sigma^2 n_1 \cdot n_2 e^{-E/RT} \times \sqrt{\bar{u}_1^2 \cdot \bar{u}_2^2}$ where $\bar{u}_1$ and $\bar{u}_2$ are the root mean square velocities of the corresponding molecules.

Assuming that each collision in which joint energy exceeds E , results in a chemical change, then the number of molecules per c.c. is

$$\pi \sigma^2 n_1 \cdot n_2 e^{-E/RT} \times \sqrt{\bar{u}_1^2 \cdot \bar{u}_2^2}$$

Assuming $\sigma = 3 \times 10^{-8}$ and $\sqrt{\bar{u}_1^2 \cdot \bar{u}_2^2}$ is of the order of 3×10^{-4} cm. and that n_1 for $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ $0.1666M = 1 \times 10^{20}$, n_2 for $\text{I}_2 = 6 \times 10^{17}$ and $e^{-E/RT} = e^{-34850/2 \times 893}$ when $T = 60^\circ$, we get the number of molecules reacting in one second per. c.c. Thus it is equal to

$$3.14 \times 9 \times 10^{-16} \times 1 \times 10^{20} \times 6 \times 10^{17} \times e^{-52.3} \times 3 \times 10^{-4} = 5 \times 10^{19} \times e^{-5.23} \\ = 5 \times 10^{19} \times 1.2 \times 10^{-19} = 6 \text{ (approximately)}$$

The whole of iodine is used up in about 90 minutes at 60° even in presence of KI. Hence, the number of molecules reacting per c.c. = 6×10^{17} . The number of molecules therefore reacting actually per second = $\frac{6 \times 10^{17}}{90 \times 60} = 1.1 \times 10^{15}$.

It is clear therefore that the observed rate is far greater than the calculated rate. The reaction therefore suggests chain mechanism.

Photochemical Reaction

The order of reaction with respect to iodine in light comes out to be one half, while it is one with respect to ammonium oxalate. The temperature coefficient is about 35 for ten degree rise of temperature. The reaction is retarded by KI, but the order of reaction does not change. The relationship between intensity and velocity shows a square-root relationship. The results are summarised below.

TABLE IV

Conc. of reactants, same as before. Temp = 50° .

Time.	$a - x$	$k_2 \times 60$	$k_0 \times 60$	$k_1 \times 60$
0 mins.	12.7	—	—	—
35	10.7	0.0168	0.067	0.0021
70	8.85	0.0168	0.055	0.0022
104	7.5	0.0158	0.050	0.0021
139	5.95	0.0161	0.048	0.0023
178	4.7	0.0158	0.044	0.0024

TABLE V

Conc of oxalate.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}^{150^\circ}$.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}^{140^\circ}$.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}^{130^\circ}$.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \frac{10}{10}$	Ratio of conc.	Ratio of $k_{\frac{1}{2}}^{50^\circ}$.
0.1666M (a)	0.0190	0.0062	0.0018	3.1	a/b=2	1.8
0.0833 (b)	0.0110	0.0034	0.0018	3.2	b/c=2	1.9
0.0416 (c)	0.0032	0.00092	0.00028	3.2		

TABLE VI

Conc. of Am. oxalate = 0.166M. Temp. = 50°.

$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ Dark	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ Distance=d	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (2d)	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (3d)
0.00030	0.0185	0.0073	0.0052
Ratio of intensity. $\frac{3^2}{2^2} = 2.25$		Ratio of I. 1.5	Ratio of velocity. $\frac{0.0070}{0.0049} = 1.4$
$\frac{2^2}{1^2} = 4$		2	$\frac{0.0182}{0.0070} = 2.6$

Photochemical After-effect

Dhar and Mukerji (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 203) have observed that the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine shows photochemical after-effect. The work has been extended by MacMahon and Lal (*ibid.*, 1940, 17, 429) and they have found that the after-effect rate increases with the length of the period of pre-illumination. Our results with ammonium oxalate and iodine show that it behaves similarly.

TABLE VII

Conc. of Am. oxalate = 0.04165 M. Conc. of I₂ = 0.000937M.
Conc. of KI = 0.00937M. Temp. = 50°.

$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ dark.	T.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (exposure, 8 min.).	T.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (exposure, 8 min.).	T.	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (exposure, 9 min.).
0.000018	30 min.	0.0000304	20 min.	0.0000604	15 min.	0.0000856
	60	0.0000302	40	0.0000492	30	0.0009776
	90	0.0000279	60	0.0000416	50	0.000680
	120	0.0000270	100	0.0000388	80	0.000583
	180	0.0000258	150	0.000252	120	0.0000481

The photochemical after-effect falls as the time after cutting off the illumination increases. Our study with different concentrations and temperatures show that after-effect increases as the period of pre-illumination is increased.

Mechanism of the Reaction

In view of the fact that the results obtained with ammonium oxalate and iodine are similar to those obtained in the case of $K_2C_2O_4$ and I_2 , it suggests itself that the mechanism of the reaction should be similar. We therefore suggest the following mechanism.

It is assumed that primary process is the atomisation of I_2 molecules. Thus,

So that when absorption is complete in total light, we have

$$\frac{d}{dt} (I_2) = k (I_0)^{\frac{1}{2}} [(NH_4)_2 C_2O_4] / [I_2]^{\frac{1}{2}} [KI]$$

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